

Notes

Aluminon as an indicator for EDTA Titration of Cupric Ions

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ALUMINON (tri-ammonium aurine tricarboxylate) has been used as an indicator for EDTA titration of cupric ions. Titrations can be accurately carried out in the pH range 2.0-3.0.

The effect of variables such as concentrations, pH, temperature and foreign ions have been investigated.

Experimental

Copper sulphate solution: A stock solution of copper sulphate (0.1M) was prepared by dissolving 24.95 g copper sulphate in distilled water and making upto 1 liter.

EDTA solution: A stock solution of 0.01M Na-salt of EDTA was prepared by dissolving 3.723 g of EDTA in 1 liter of distilled water.

Indicator solution: 1.0% solution was prepared from pure sample of the reagent by dissolving the requisite amount in distilled water.

Metal solutions: To study the interference of various foreign ions in the estimation of Cu^{2+} with EDTA, the corresponding analytical quality of salts were taken and their 0.2M solutions prepared in distilled water.

Aluminon gives a pink colour with cupric ions. There is a sharp colour change on titration with EDTA from pink to light green as the end point approaches.

Effect of pH: When an aliquot of Cu^{2+} is titrated with EDTA, copper can be estimated accurately in the pH range 2.0-3.0 with the help of the indicators investigated.

Effect of Indicator concentration: Titrations were carried out with different concentrations of the indicator. It was found that an addition of 2 drops of 1.0% solution of the indicator gave satisfactory results.

Effect of Temperature: The titration could be satisfactorily carried out in the temperature range 10°-60°.

Effect of Foreign Ions: To investigate the effect of foreign ions, titrations of synthetic solutions were

carried out at pH 2.0 maintaining the pH by acetate-HCl buffer. Preliminary investigations indicated that PO_4^{3-} , AsO_4^{3-} , S^{2-} , $\text{Fr}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$, CNS^- , CrO_4^{2-} , Fe^{3+} , Ni^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Al^{3+} interfere seriously. It was observed that at 1.3 mg concentration of copper, 10 times excess of Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Mg^{2+} , Cl^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} could be tolerated.

Suggested procedure: Take a 5.0 ml aliquot of solution containing cupric ions, adjust pH 2.0-3.0 using acetate-HCl buffer of pH 2.0, add 2 drops of 1.0% solution of indicator and titrate against 0.01M solution of EDTA with vigorous stirring to light green colour.

Standard Deviation: Five, 5.0 ml aliquots of 0.01M copper sulphate were analysed according to the suggested procedure. The standard deviation was 1.0%.

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Spectral Studies in Oxouranium(V) Compounds

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COORDINATION complexes of U(V) with nitrogen and oxygen donor ligands have been characterised¹⁻⁴. The complex, $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH})_2\text{UOCl}_5$ has been shown to be an equimolar mixture of UCl_5^{2-} and $\text{UO}_2\text{Cl}_4^{2-}$ complexes⁵. The oxochloro complexes of U(V) of the formulae, M_2UOCl_5 [$\text{M} = (\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_4\text{As}^6$, Cs^7 , $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}^{8-9}$], $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}]_2\text{UOCl}_5$, phthalazine⁷, $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}]_2\text{UOCl}_5$ bis (1,10-phenanthroline)⁷ and $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH})_2\text{UOCl}_5 \cdot 2.5\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NHCl}^6$ have been synthesised and characterised by spectral measurements. In the present paper the oxochloro complexes of U(V) of the type, $(\text{BH})_2\text{UOCl}_5$ (B = pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline, α -picoline and β -picoline) have been isolated from UCl_5 solution in SOCl_2 and characterised by IR, reflectance and ESR spectra.

Experimental

UCl_5 was prepared by refluxing UO_3 or UO_2Cl_2 with SOCl_2 .¹⁻³ Pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline, α -picoline and β -picoline (BDH AnalyR) were purified as already reported². Compounds of U(V) are very

sensitive to moisture, therefore, filtration and drying have been carried out in dry atmosphere. Petroleum ether was dried by usual method and kept over sodium.

Pyridine, quinoline or isoquinoline (undried), cooled in an ice bath was added to an ice cooled solution of UCl_5 in $SOCl_2$ in a base/ UCl_5 molar ratio of 2 : 1. Yellow solid in case of pyridine and reddish brown solids in the case of other bases, separated out on the addition of petroleum ether. These solids were repeatedly washed with dry petroleum ether and dried in vacuum. Picolines (undried) react vigorously with $SOCl_2$, therefore these bases were diluted with CCl_4 before addition to UCl_5 solution in $SOCl_2$. The analyses have been recorded in table 1.

Reflectance spectra of the pyridinium, quinolinium and isoquinolinium complexes show a sharp band at about 16665 cm^{-1} . This band is perhaps due to $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8$ transition which has moved to a much higher energy in $(BH)_2UOCl_5$ compared to its position at $11,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in UCl_5 . This is in agreement with the theoretical predictions⁷. However, some disproportionation during measurements is unavoidable and peaks also appear at 15625 cm^{-1} and 13158 cm^{-1} which correspond to U(IV).

ESR measurements on $(PYH)_2UOCl_5$, $(QH)_2UOCl_5$ and $(IQH)_2UOCl_5$ (PY = pyridine, Q = quinoline and IQ = isoquinoline) produce strong and broad signal between 5900–5950 Gauss giving 'g' values of 1.12, 1.13 and 1.13 respectively. These 'g' values

TABLE I—URANIUM (V) OXOCHLORO COMPLEXES

S.No.	Complex	Analytical Results					
		Found %			Required %		
		U	Cl	N	U	Cl	N
1.	$(C_5H_5NH)_2UOCl_5$	39.91	29.80	4.70	40.24	30.01	4.73
2.	$(C_5H_7NH)_2*UOCl_5$	34.15	25.47	3.99	34.41	25.67	4.05
3.	$(C_5H_7NH)_2**UOCl_5$	34.21	25.43	3.95	34.41	25.67	4.05
4.	$(C_5H_7NH)_2***UOCl_5$	38.31	28.43	4.50	38.42	28.65	4.52
5.	$(C_5H_7NH)_2****UOCl_5$	38.20	28.34	4.45	38.42	28.65	4.52

* = quinolinium, ** = isoquinolinium, *** = α -picolinium, **** = β -picolinium.

Uranium was estimated gravimetrically as well as volumetrically². Chlorine was estimated volumetrically by Volhard's method. Nitrogen was determined in the microanalytical laboratory.

IR, reflectance and ESR spectra were recorded on spectrophotometers already described².

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of the oxochloro complexes correspond to $(BH)_2UOCl_5$. These complexes are stable under anhydrous conditions and disproportionate into U(IV) and U(VI) in moisture. On thermal decomposition these complexes give U_3O_8 at about 600° .

The IR spectra of the complexes in nujol mulls have been recorded. A strong band at $2845, 2835\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a broad band between $2925\text{--}2825$ and $2925\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ conforms to BH^+ ⁹ (B = pyridine, isoquinoline, quinoline and β -picoline respectively). A very strong band in all these oxochloro complexes at 910 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the $U=O$ stretching frequency^{6,7}.

are in good agreement with the calculated and experimental values of 1.04⁷ and 1.09^{7,8} for $[(C_5H_5)_4N]_2UOCl_5$ indicating similar arrangement around Uranium(V) in these complexes.

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